

Principles of Formation of Social and Cultural Competence of Students in the Process of Literary Education

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Abstract:

The article refers to the main principles and aspects of the formation of socio-cultural competence of students.

Key words: literary education, socio-cultural competence, cognitive, competence, modernization, intellectual ability, technology, communicative competence.

It is appropriate to form and master the model of national culture using the artifacts of universal culture as the main tool in the development of socio-cultural competence of students in general secondary education schools, with the following means:

1. Posters, diagrams, documentaries, etc. on the basis of national culture.
2. Art works.
3. Examples of fiction.
4. Works related to cinematography and music.
5. Encyclopedic references, scientific-methodical literature, reviews, guidelines, maps.
6. Mass media.
7. Communicating with the teacher about other people's culture as a translator.
8. Explanations, systematic functional generalizations, speech, etiquette standards, non-verbal means of communication, aphorisms, phraseological units, non-equivalent lexemes, etc., about the integral component of national and universal culture. Accordingly, it can be estimated that

the content of the epistemological approach in the literary education system consists of the following aspects.

1. **Developmental aspect** (developing a flexible translation epistemological thinking and translation motivation in the process of intercultural dialogue, which allows to overcome stereotypes and penetrate into the culture of the country whose literature is being studied, to develop mechanisms of intercultural differentiation, to expect predictions).
2. **Academic aspect** (social-cultural concepts of education, skills, ability and experience of using educational concepts related to socio-cultural situations in the process of solving translation problems);
3. **Cognitive aspect** (the expansion of epistemics is based on the comparative development of concepts related to the socio-cultural worldview).
4. **Educational aspect** (value directions of the future) translator, socio-cultural education and broad worldview, translation responsibility, tolerance).

In other researches, it is observed that other edges of the problem were analyzed. In particular, D.G.Shumakov's algorithm for the formation of socio-cultural competence is given as follows:

1. *Introductory stage of motivation.* It is required to determine the amount of socio-cultural knowledge of students.
2. Acquainting students with *social and cultural events and facts* in the country whose literature is being studied. The socio-cultural features of the studied language, speech and non-speech behavior are acquired, and primary speech skills are formed by performing receptive and reproductive exercises.

Modernization of the continuous education system in the current globalization conditions is not limited to the traditions acquired in the field of education over the years, but taking into account the development of social society, following modern technologies, using advanced foreign experiences, and an integrative approach to all stages of education. , requires the improvement of the software of the state policy on digitalization of education. In this regard, pedagogues have a great responsibility to constantly search for themselves.

However, modern requirements are such that special professional competencies are not enough for a modern pedagogue. In addition to special professional competencies, teachers are required to acquire the following basic competencies during their methodical, methodological and pedagogical activities. These competencies are distinguished by their reflexive, cognitive, diagnostic, communicative and social nature. Below we will discuss each of these competencies in more detail.

1. *Reflexive competence* depends on the pedagogue's ability to evaluate his work with an integral, essential ability. It's about being able to see the cause-and-effect relationships between its tasks, goals, means, conditions, and results. The pedagogue moves from the assessment of some pedagogical abilities to the assessment of the effectiveness of his own skills and activities.

Self-knowledge of educators is formed on the basis of a combination of all components of experience, knowledge of other people and self. In this case, self-evaluation opens the way to understanding the reasons for one's own creative achievements and failures, the specific demands for achievements and shortcomings of one's personality and activity.

Pedagogical reflection – is the logical and creative ability to constantly analyze professional activity, to evaluate each stage in methodical activity. Interests and spiritual needs form the basis of the orientation that perceives the creative individuality of the teacher. They can include recognition of the need for general, special and psychological-pedagogical knowledge and their importance.

The motivation of professional-pedagogical self-improvement, which is carried out in the course of activity, includes the awareness of positive consequences, social significance and the value of one's own achievements. The effectiveness of the application of the motivation function requires the creation of conditions and encouraging stimuli that are the basis for final results and creative independent development.

2. *Cognitive competence* is characterized by the readiness to constantly improve one's professional level, the ability to independently acquire new knowledge and skills, to apply creative development ideas, and to regularly enrich one's methodical competence.

3. *Informational competence*, in addition to the special and professional-pedagogical knowledge and thinking methods of the teacher, it envisages the acquisition of special skills in obtaining, processing and using the necessary information in the process of professional activity. In this regard, the acquisition of new information technologies aimed at achieving educational diagnosis by using a set of functionally subordinate pedagogical, informational, methodological, psychophysiological tools and methods has a special place.

The importance of the acquisition of information competence is that the pedagogue can take into account the advantages of the student, achieve a systematic view of the educational activity of each student in the use of multi-level textbooks, automated teaching and control systems.

4. *Communicative competence* describes the characteristics of the teacher's communicative activity. It includes techniques to help achieve high-level communication. Being able to understand the role of others in communication, showing interest in his personality, being able to explain his inner state in terms of behavioral aspects, mastering non-verbal means of communication (mimicry, gestures), rhetorical methods, evaluator, especially in the teaching process the superiority of the democratic style, the ability to look at some aspects of the pedagogical situation with humor.

5. *Social competence* is a manifestation of the connection with the needs of the educational institution and society as an indicator of the ability to understand the social importance of increasing the level of methodical training, take responsibility for the proposed new methodical approaches and their application. It describes moral culture, ideals, spiritual values.

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